

Workplace Harassment: A case of the University of Balochistan

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Abstract

The impact of harassment on female students' empowerment, academic performance, and general well-being is the main emphasis of this study, which looks at the difficulties experienced by these students at the University of Balochistan. The study draws attention to the social and cultural constraints that worsen gender inequality and make it dangerous for women to pursue higher education. Seventy female BS students from different departments participated in the study, which found that many of them encounter physical, verbal, and sexual harassment both on and off campus. The results show that harassment has a negative impact on students' mental health in addition to impeding their academic performance and making some of them think about dropping out. The study emphasizes how important it is to have strong reporting procedures, supportive networks, and a focus on female role models in order to create a more secure and welcoming learning environment. The University of Balochistan can greatly enhance the educational experience and results for its female students by tackling these problems, which would also help the region's economy and society as a whole.

Keywords: Harassment , Female Empowerment and Academic Performance, Gender Inequality in Education, Mental Health and Student Well-being, University Safety and Reporting Procedures.

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